

Atrial fibrillation in a pregnant patient without structural heart disease: a case report

Fibrilación auricular en una paciente gestante sin cardiopatía estructural: reporte de caso clínico

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Abstract

Las arritmias cardíacas son complicaciones frecuentes durante el embarazo en mujeres consideradas previamente sanas, con o sin cardiopatía orgánica de base, siendo más comunes las supraventriculares. Su manejo representa un desafío por el elevado riesgo de presentar eventos adversos maternos y fetales, tanto por la arritmia en sí misma, como por los medicamentos usados para el tratamiento. Se relata el caso clínico de una paciente obstétrica de 24 años con embarazo de 18.3 semanas, que desarrolla fibrilación auricular con descompensación hemodinámica durante su estancia hospitalaria, a consecuencia de sepsis de origen urinario. Se realiza tratamiento farmacológico, presentando tanto la madre como el feto una evolución favorable. El embarazo puede asociarse con arritmias potencialmente letales y la conducta a adoptar debe ser inmediata buscando salvaguardar el bienestar materno-fetal. La literatura es escasa acerca del manejo de arritmias durante el embarazo, se propone analizar los elementos para el correcto tratamiento de la fibrilación auricular durante la gestación.

Palabras clave: Fibrilación Atrial; Embarazo; Propafenona; Sepsis.

Resumen

Cardiac arrhythmias are a frequent complication during pregnancy in women previously considered healthy, independent of prior history of organic heart disease, the most common being supraventricular arrhythmias. Its management represents a challenge due to the associated high risk of maternal and fetal adverse events resulting from the arrhythmia itself or the drugs used for treatment. The present case involves a 24-year-old obstetric patient with an 18.3-week pregnancy who develops atrial fibrillation with hemodynamic instability during her in-hospital stay due to urosepsis. Pharmacologic treatment was performed, resulting in a favorable evolution for the mother and the fetus. Pregnancy can be associated with potentially lethal arrhythmias, and the adopted behavior in these cases should be immediate, seeking to safeguard maternal-fetal wellbeing. The literature is scarce on the management of arrhythmias during pregnancy. Here, we propose to analyze the elements for the correct treatment of atrial fibrillation during pregnancy.

Keywords: Atrial Fibrillation; Pregnancy, Propafenone, Sepsis.

Normal pregnancy is accompanied by significant hemodynamic and physiologic changes oriented towards fulfilling the requirements of developing a new human being. One of the most significant modifications occurs within the cardiovascular system, with a 40% increment in blood volume and a 40 to 50% increment in cardiac output (CO), mainly due to increased stroke volume. Similarly, cardiac frequency increases from the 20th to the 32nd week, maintaining its rate until 2-5 days after delivery¹.

Cardiac arrhythmias are relatively frequent during pregnancy, particularly supraventricular arrhythmias, which can be de novo or exacerbations of previously established cardioelectric alterations, producing maternal-fetal harm. The physiopathology of arrhythmias during pregnancy is unclear, but the conjunction of hemodynamic, hormonal, and autonomic changes have been considered the likely cause².

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is one of the most frequent cardiac arrhythmias³. Hemodynamic anomalies and thromboembolic events related to AF are the main contributors to its high morbimortality⁴. In pregnant patients, AF can produce hemodynamic instability and increase the risk of adverse outcomes for the mother and the fetus.

In the initial evaluation of a patient with cardiac arrhythmias, the assessment of any underlying condition is necessary. Furthermore, potentially reversible arrhythmic conditions should be treated. These may include hydroelectrolytic disorders, hyperthyroidism, excessive consumption of alcohol, caffeine, tobacco, infections, acute stress, and usage of sympathomimetic drugs⁵. Here, we present the case of a pregnant patient without any previously known structural heart disease with AF.

CASE REPORT

A 24-year-old patient, single, born and resident of Sigchos, mixed race, with basic instruction, housewife, without relevant pathologic history. Among her gynecologic history, she reports normal menarche at 14 years, regular five-day long menstrual cycles, sexarche at 14 years, two sexual partners. She refers no history of sexually transmitted diseases and no family planning. Two previous pregnancies, the prior pregnancy evolved satisfactorily and was delivered by eutocic vaginal delivery without complications. Current gestation with 18.3 weeks of gestational age as calculated by the last menstrual period, without complications. At physical examination, the following was observed: Weight: 53.7kg, height: 154 cm, BMI: 22.6 kg/m², blood pressure: 73/36 mmHg; heart rate: 115 bpm; respiratory rate: 24 bpm; oxygen saturation: 92%.

The patient was conscious, oriented, and febrile. She had a noncongestive oropharynx, rhythmic heart sounds with-

out murmurs, normal vesicular breath sounds without abnormal sounds. Soft abdomen, depressible, painful in both iliac fosses, normal bowel sounds, gravid uterus with a single fetus, alive, fetal heart rate 148 bpm, without uterine activity. Normal external genitalia with chunky fetid vaginal secretion, posteriorly located and closed cervix. Nonedematous extremities, distant pulses present.

Her current illness was characterized by colic abdominal pain in the right iliac fossa of moderate intensity lasting several days, which led to consulting a private physician who prescribed ambulatory drugs for urinary infections; however, the patient did not follow the instructions. The pain increased and was associated with urinary symptomatology and general weakness. As a result, the patient consulted the gynecology emergency, where she was diagnosed with urinary origin sepsis with mixed vaginitis. Rehydration was administered, as well as antibiotic therapy, and the patient was relocated into the intensive care unit because of the hemodynamic instability, where she received vasoactive support and intravenous piperacillin/tazobactam 4.5 g every 6 hours. She presented tachycardia during her second hospitalization day; consequently, an electrocardiogram (ECG) was requested and revealed an AF with a normal ventricular response. A cardiology consult was requested to assess the patient. The patient was hemodynamically stable and had no signs of low CO alongside a normal cardiovascular exam. A second ECG revealed an arrhythmic pattern with 150 bpm, therefore labelling it as an AF with a rapid ventricular response (Figure 1). Furthermore, an echocardiogram was performed, but no abnormal findings were reported, leading to the conclusion that AF was secondary to sepsis and the use of vasoactive drugs. It was suggested to use adenosine in case of hemodynamic instability and 150 mg of propafenone administered orally every 8 hours, which, alongside the resolution of the infectious process, resulted in a good clinical evolution, reaching sinus rhythm on the 10th day. Avoiding new infections and vaginal delivery at term was suggested unless contraindicated by the obstetrics service. The patient was periodically assessed in the consult service of gynecology and cardiology, reporting no recurrence of the arrhythmia.

Complementary exams

Blood analytics: Leukocytes: 46,800 x mm³, segmented: 87%, lymphocytes: 9.2%, hemoglobin: 11.4 g/dL, hematocrit: 31.8%, platelets: 59,000 x mm³, glucose: 110 mg/dL, creatinine: 1.2 mg/dL, total bilirubin: 2.24, direct bilirubin: 1.44, indirect bilirubin: 0.8, negative HIV test, nonreactive VDRL. Arterial gasometry: pH 7.46, pCO₂: 20, HCO₃ 14.1, lactate: 3.53, sodium: 133.3, potassium: 3.03, chloride: 112.

Elemental and microscopic urine analysis: pH 5, density 1025, proteins 30, leukocytes +++, pyocytes 80-100, bacteria +++, epithelial cells 2-3, gram negative bacilli ++, Gram and analysis of vaginal secretion: pyocytes +, fungi +, yeast +, bacteria +, amine test negative, decreased Doderlein flora, gram positive cocci +, scarce gram negative bacilli.

Obstetric ultrasound: pregnant uterus with a single, alive, fetus in pelvic position with normal motility and tonus. Fetal heart rate 147 bpm, BPD 3.9 cm, HC 15.5cm, AC 13.3 cm, FL 2.3 cm, 18.1 weeks of gestational age, 232 +/- 34 grams, anterior placenta grade 1/3 maturity, adequate amount of amniotic fluid.

Figure 1. 12-lead electrocardiogram: non-sinus rhythm, heart rate at 147 bpm. PR interval unquantifiable (complete absence of P wave), 0.08 seconds QRS, and 0.36 seconds QT interval. Electrocardiogram pattern suggests atrial fibrillation with rapid ventricular response.

Heart ultrasound: Geometry and biventricular systolic function are preserved. LVEF 59%, LV and RV with adequate diameters and volumes, no thrombus, masses, or effusions. Mild tricuspid and mitral insufficiency, with systolic pressure of the RV at 27 mmHg. Valvular planes where explored in conventional views and in modified two-dimensional and color Doppler views. Color doppler reported no suggestive findings of vegetations, thus concluding that AF was secondary to the septic process and vasoactive drugs.

treat the origin; in addition, the risk of intracardiac thrombi demands the consideration of anticoagulation therapy¹⁰, where the patient must be informed of the risk and benefits of such therapy. Furthermore, in every case of pregnancy-associated AF, an exhaustive evaluation must be performed to rule out the presence of any underlying structural heart disease¹¹.

The appearance of a cardiac arrhythmia might be related to the usage of drugs that stimulate the electrical activity of the heart. For instance, the usage of adrenalin directly interacts with α and β adrenergic receptors, producing potent positive inotropic effects needed in patients with shock requiring hemodynamic support. However, usage of this drug must be strictly monitored, given that it can produce tachycardia and auricular or ventricular arrhythmias (fibrillation and extrasystoles, respectively). As a result of the α -receptor agonist effect, the risk of vasoconstriction-induced ischemia significantly increases in diverse territories, probably causing: pulmonary arterial hypertension, oliguria because of renal impairment, and vasoconstriction of uterine arteries¹².

During pregnancy, AF can produce significant hemodynamic instability, increasing maternal-fetal morbimortality¹³. The increased cardiac demand during pregnancy can result in less tolerance towards AF. Evaluating other variables like underlying heart diseases and the associated ventricular response is also necessary³. Clinically, patients with AF usually complain of palpitations, and in worse cases, they can have thoracic pain, dyspnea, weakness, dizziness, and syncope¹⁴. In this particular case, symptoms were mild, resulting in a treatment to control heart rate exclusively.

Several drugs have been reported as safe during pregnancy to control AF, with beta-blockers being the drug category most extensively studied and implemented to control arrhythmias during pregnancy. Metoprolol and propranolol have an acceptable risk profile but are not entirely safe during the first trimester. Nonetheless, they are considered safe during the second and third trimesters of pregnancy¹⁵. Non-dihydropyridine calcium channel blockers (CCB) such as verapamil and diltiazem are also relatively safe during pregnancy. Verapamil is mainly implemented to acutely interrupt supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) during pregnancy⁴.

Propafenone is a class Ic antiarrhythmic drug that crosses the placental barrier and excels at pharmacologic conversion and maintaining sinus rhythm during pregnancy¹⁶. Although its implementation is controversial, 150-200 mg three times per day has shown outstanding results, as administered in the present case, without significant adverse effects for the mother or the fetus^{4,17}. Before administering any antiarrhythmic drug, the presence of underlying structural heart disease must be ruled out¹⁷.

Amiodarone is a class III antiarrhythmic that can be orally administered for the long-term maintenance of sinus rhythm. However, it is contraindicated during pregnancy

Maternal and fetal safety are the priority in the treatment of AF during pregnancy. Therapeutic management in pregnant women presenting with de novo AF is primarily based on the same principles applied to non-pregnant patients, with a rapid approach and surveillance of antiarrhythmic drugs, which need to be cautiously implemented due to possible fetal harm⁶. AF is rare among women of fertile age, but this condition can be associated with other systemic processes, especially in young women with structurally normal hearts⁷. Moreover, Hu et al.⁸ described that patients with septicemia or septic shock have a much greater risk of developing de novo AF.

The natural history of AF is benign, most of the patients spontaneously return to sinus rhythm in less than 24 hours after proper control of heart rate⁹. For those with persistent AF, it is necessary to establish the etiology and

due to its association with fetal bradycardia, thyroid dysfunction and fetal anomalies^{18,19} (Table 1).

Table 1. Safety of antiarrhythmic drugs during pregnancy

Safe to use/Extensive data
Sotalol
Digoxin
Moderate safety/Extensive experience
Propranolol
Metoprolol
Labetalol
Verapamil
Use with caution
Propafenone
Ibutilide
Atenolol
Recommended against during pregnancy
Amiodarone
Dofetilide
Ivabradine

In the case of AF-induced hemodynamic instability or significant maternal-fetal adverse outcome risks, synchronized electrical cardioversion with 50-100 J is usually successful⁷. Several case reports have demonstrated that cardioversion can satisfactorily reverse maternal AF without harming the fetus. Energetic requirements are similar in pregnant and non-pregnant women²⁰. Hemodynamic instability was rapidly overcome in the present case, thus not needing to implement cardioversion.

Anticoagulation therapy must be guided by assessing thromboembolic risk, given that heparin or warfarin therapy are significantly associated with increased maternal and fetal morbidity. Increased risk of hemorrhagic complications must always be considered during pregnancy and the peripartum period in women treated with anticoagulation regimens²⁰. The additional risk of thromboembolism attributable to pregnancy in pregnant women with AF is unknown. However, it is vital to consider pregnancy as a hypercoagulable state associated with increased production of coagulation factors.

Conclusions

Pregnancy increases the susceptibility to develop AF due to physiologic, hormonal, and autonomic modifications. Likewise, underlying structural heart disease or systemic conditions commonly present in fertile women might also increase the risk of developing AF during pregnancy. AF can cause significant hemodynamic adverse changes, hampering maternal-fetal well-being. Early detection and proper etiologic identification and treatment can be the bedrock of the treatment of AF during pregnancy. Moreover, a thorough clinical exploration and high clinical suspicion are needed to detect this condition promptly.

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